

The Influence of Meteorological Parameters on Groundwater Radon Concentration in Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of meteorological parameters on groundwater radon (^{222}Rn) concentration in Oyo State, South-Western Nigeria. Groundwater samples were collected from wells and boreholes across different depths, ranging from shallow to moderate–deep aquifers (10–70 m). Radon measurements were performed using a RAD7 water measurement setup and the Durrige RAD7 radon detector. Meteorological data, including wind speed, rainfall, temperature, relative humidity, and atmospheric pressure, were obtained from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) database and synchronized with sampling periods. Descriptive statistics, graphical analysis, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were applied to assess spatial and depth-related variability in radon concentration, while Pearson correlation and multiple regression analyses were used to quantify relationships with meteorological factors. The results show that groundwater radon concentrations ranged from 485.72 to 6205.22 Bq/m³, with higher levels in moderate–deep aquifer layers. Depth showed the strongest positive influence on radon levels ($R=0.65$; $B=486.196$; $\text{Beta}=0.355$; $p=0.016$), while relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, and rainfall acted as secondary controls through dilution, degassing, and recharge processes. Temperature exhibited a weak and non-significant effect ($R=-0.12$). The results also demonstrate that aquifer depth is the primary control on groundwater radon concentration, with meteorological parameters modifying levels in secondary ways. These findings highlight the importance of considering both hydrogeological and environmental factors in radon risk assessments, emphasizing the need for continuous monitoring to mitigate potential radiological health risks.

Keywords: groundwater radon, meteorological parameters, Oyo State, RAD7, depth influence, ANOVA, correlation analysis

INTRODUCTION

Radon (^{222}Rn) is a naturally occurring radioactive noble gas produced from the alpha decay of radium (^{226}Ra) in the uranium (^{238}U) decay series, with a half-life of about 3.82 days. Being chemically inert, radon can migrate easily through soil and rock pores via recoil, diffusion, and advective transport, eventually dissolving in groundwater (UNSCEAR, 2008). Radon in groundwater is of environmental and health concern because it contributes to radiation exposure through ingestion and inhalation when released into indoor air during domestic water use (WHO, 2017; Isinkaye et al., 2021). Prolonged exposure to elevated

radon concentrations has been associated with increased risk of lung cancer (Darby et al., 2005; ICRP, 2014). Groundwater radon concentration varies widely depending on geological and hydrogeological conditions. Factors such as lithology, uranium content of rocks, aquifer depth, permeability, and water–rock interaction time significantly influence radon levels in groundwater (Appleton, 2007; Schubert et al., 2012). Areas underlain by granitic or metamorphic rocks generally show higher radon concentrations due to elevated uranium content, while structural features such as fractures and faults can enhance radon migration into aquifers (Przylibski, 2011). In Nigeria, studies have reported varying radon concentrations in

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

groundwater across different geological settings. Relatively low concentrations within recommended limits have been reported in Lagos State (Abdulkareem & Ademola, 2019), whereas elevated levels exceeding guideline values have been observed in parts of Kwara State (Jimoh & Ademola, 2023). Similarly, investigations in Ogun State revealed generally moderate concentrations with localized exceedances (Fatoki & Ademola, 2021). Other studies have also confirmed that groundwater radon levels in southwestern Nigeria are largely controlled by geological composition and aquifer characteristics (Ademola & Olatunji, 2016; Isinkaye & Emelue, 2015). However, these studies mainly focus on spatial distribution and radiological risk, with limited consideration of atmospheric and climatic factors that may influence radon variability. Meteorological parameters such as atmospheric pressure, rainfall, temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity are known to influence radon transport and concentration in environmental systems (Fujiyoshi et al., 2002; Nazaroff & Nero, 1988). Variations in atmospheric pressure affect pressure gradients between the subsurface and the atmosphere, thereby influencing radon exhalation and migration (Schery & Gaeddert, 1984). Rainfall can also influence radon levels by mobilizing radon from soil pores into groundwater or by diluting concentrations during intense recharge events (Sundal et al., 2008; García-Tobar, 2013). Wind speed and relative humidity affect soil-atmosphere gas exchange processes, while temperature influences radon solubility and diffusion rates (Pinza-Molina et al., 2018; Spasić & Gulan, 2022; Huang et al., 2024). Although numerous studies

worldwide have examined the relationship between meteorological conditions and radon variability, most of these investigations have been conducted in temperate regions (Zmazek et al., 2003; Chambers et al., 2015). In Nigeria, the combined influence of meteorological parameters on groundwater radon concentration remains largely unexplored. Therefore, this study investigates the influence of key meteorological parameters on groundwater radon concentration in Oyo State, southwestern Nigeria, using field measurements and statistical analysis to identify the dominant environmental controls on radon variability in tropical groundwater systems.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Oyo State, South-Western Nigeria, located within the Precambrian Basement Complex, which is characterized by uranium-bearing rocks that contribute to groundwater radon occurrence. Oyo State lies approximately between latitudes 7°00'N and 9°00'N and longitudes 2°30'E and 4°30'E, and is bounded by Kwara State to the north, Osun State to the east, Ogun State to the south, and the Republic of Benin to the west. The area experiences a tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons, which influence groundwater recharge and radon transport. Geologically, the region is predominantly underlain by crystalline basement complex rocks known to host uranium- and radium-bearing minerals, enhancing radon generation in groundwater. The spatial distribution of sampling locations in Oyo State is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A map showing the GPS location of Oyo State (nigeriagalleria.com)

Groundwater samples were collected from selected wells and boreholes across the state to ensure spatial representation. Sampling points were categorized into depth-based layers ranging from shallow to moderate and deeper aquifers (approximately 10–70 m) to evaluate the influence of aquifer depth on radon concentration. Radon measurements were performed using a DurrIDGE RAD7 system. The experimental setup for radon extraction from water samples is

illustrated in Figure 2, while the RAD7 detection unit is shown in Figure 3. Groundwater samples were collected in airtight containers to minimize radon loss and analyzed shortly after collection. During measurement, radon was degassed from water into a closed-loop air system and quantified using alpha spectrometry. All measurements were recorded in Bq/m³, and the instrument was calibrated according to the manufacturer’s specifications.

Figure 2: A RAD7 set up for measuring ²²²Rn water samples

Figure 3: DurrIDGE Rad7 Machine (DURRIDGE, 2015)

Meteorological parameters considered in this study include wind speed, rainfall, air temperature, relative humidity, and atmospheric pressure. These data were obtained from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) database, for the period and location of radon measurement. The data were synchronized with groundwater sampling periods to ensure temporal consistency. Descriptive statistics

and graphical analyses were used to assess groundwater radon distribution and its relationship with meteorological parameters. The statistical significance of variations in radon concentration with respect to meteorological factors and groundwater depth was evaluated using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 5% significance level. Total variance was expressed as (1)

$$SS_T = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (x_{ij} - \bar{x})^2 \quad (1)$$

where x_{ij} represents the radon concentration of the j th observation in the i th group, \bar{x} is the overall mean, k is the number of groups and n_i is the number of observations in each group. The between-group and within-group sums of squares were computed using the expression (2) and (3) respectively.

$$SS_B = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (2)$$

$$SS_W = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_i)^2 \quad (1)$$

The corresponding mean squares were obtained from $MS_B = SS_B / (k - 1)$ and $MS_W = SS_W / (N - k)$, while the F-statistic was determined using $F = MS_B / MS_W$ at $p < 0.05$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of groundwater radon concentrations using descriptive statistics, graphical trends, and ANOVA (shown in Table 1) revealed substantial variability across layers due to the combined effects of meteorological factors and aquifer characteristics. Figure 4 shows the relationship between radon concentration and meteorological parameters: (a) wind speed, (b) rainfall, (c) temperature, (d) relative humidity, (e) depth, and (f) atmospheric pressure. Mean groundwater radon concentration ranges from 485.72 Bq/m³ to 6205.22 Bq/m³, indicating pronounced spatial variability within the study area. Elevated radon concentrations were recorded in Layers 3 and 4, while lower values occurred in shallower layers, particularly Layer 7. The ANOVA result for radon concentration confirms that this variation is statistically significant (Table 1), demonstrating that radon distribution in groundwater is non-uniform and influenced by environmental factors. Groundwater depth shows a statistically significant influence on radon concentration (Table 1). Both the tabulated data and the depth–radon plot (Figure 4(e)) indicate that radon concentration

increases with depth up to moderate–deep aquifer levels (approximately 40–60 m). This trend is attributed to increased water–rock interaction and prolonged contact with uranium-bearing minerals at greater depths. In contrast, shallow aquifers exhibit lower radon levels due to enhanced dilution and degassing near the surface. Atmospheric pressure exhibits a strong inverse relationship with radon concentration, supported by a significant ANOVA result (Table 1). As shown in Figure 4(f), lower pressure conditions correspond to higher radon concentrations, as reduced pressure facilitates radon exhalation from soil and fractured rock into groundwater. Higher pressure conditions suppress radon migration, leading to reduced concentrations. Groundwater temperature remains relatively stable across the study area, ranging from 30.41 to 31.38 °C. Although graphical analysis suggests a weak inverse relationship between temperature and radon concentration (Figure 4(c)), the ANOVA result indicates that temperature does not have a statistically significant effect (Table 1). The narrow temperature range associated with the tropical climate of Oyo State likely limits temperature-driven variations in radon solubility and diffusion, rendering temperature a secondary control factor. Relative humidity shows the strongest statistical influence on radon concentration among all parameters considered (Table 1). Figure 4(d) shows that higher radon concentrations are generally associated with moderate relative humidity levels, while very high humidity corresponds to reduced radon concentration. This trend suggests that increased humidity, often linked to enhanced groundwater recharge, promotes dilution of radon within aquifers. Rainfall also significantly affects radon concentration, as indicated by the ANOVA results (Table 1). As illustrated in Figure 4(b), moderate rainfall levels correspond to elevated radon concentrations, indicating enhanced mobilization of radon from soil gas into groundwater during recharge events. However, higher rainfall intensities result in lower radon concentrations due to dilution effects, producing a nonlinear rainfall–radon relationship. Wind speed exhibits a statistically significant inverse relationship with radon concentration (Table 1). Figure 4(a) shows that higher wind speeds enhance soil–atmosphere gas exchange, allowing radon to escape before dissolving into groundwater. Lower wind speeds favor radon retention within the

subsurface, leading to higher groundwater concentrations. Generally, the integrated tabular, graphical, and ANOVA analyses demonstrate that groundwater radon concentration in Oyo State is significantly influenced by relative humidity, wind speed, atmospheric pressure, rainfall, and depth, while temperature plays a comparatively weak and

statistically insignificant role. These findings highlight the importance of meteorological variability in controlling groundwater radon levels and suggest potential seasonal fluctuations, underscoring the need for continuous monitoring to mitigate potential radiological health risks.

Figure 4: Groundwater radon concentration in relation to (a) wind speed, (b) rainfall, (c) temperature, (d) relative humidity, (e) depth, and (f) atmospheric pressure in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 1: ANOVA results for groundwater radon and meteorological parameters in Oyo State, Nigeria.

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Radon (Bq/m ³)	Between Groups	386969819.99	7	55281402.85	4.488	.000
	Within Groups	1133290154.7	92	12318371.247		
	Total	1520259974.71	99			
Depth (m)	Between Groups	7111.388	7	1015.913	4.040	.001
	Within Groups	23135.362	92	251.471		
	Total	30246.750	99			
Temperature	Between Groups	11.787	7	1.684	2.069	.055
	Within Groups	74.872	92	.814		
	Total	86.659	99			
Pressure	Between Groups	.568	7	.081	10.463	.000
	Within Groups	.713	92	.008		
	Total	1.281	99			
Wind speed	Between Groups	39.345	7	5.621	14.182	.000
	Within Groups	36.463	92	.396		

	Total	75.808	99			
Rainfall	Between Groups	173.312	7	24.759	5.542	.000
	Within Groups	411.005	92	4.467		
	Total	584.317	99			
Relative Humidity	Between Groups	4564.558	7	652.080	53.845	.000
	Within Groups	1114.154	92	12.110		
	Total	5678.712	99			

3.1 Percentage Contribution of Studied Parameters to Radon Variability

The percentage contribution of the studied parameters to radon variability, based on the ANOVA F-values, is presented in Figure 2. Relative humidity has the highest contribution of 59.7% ($F = 53.845$), indicating that it is the dominant factor influencing radon concentration. Wind speed contributes 15.7% ($F = 14.182$), while atmospheric pressure accounts for 11.6% ($F = 10.463$), showing that atmospheric

conditions significantly affect radon variation. Rainfall contributes 6.1% ($F = 5.542$) and depth contributes 6.8% ($F = 4.040$), suggesting moderate influence on radon levels. Temperature shows the least contribution of 2.3% ($F = 2.069$), indicating a minimal effect on radon variability. Overall, the results demonstrate that meteorological factors, particularly relative humidity, wind speed, and pressure, play the most significant roles in controlling radon concentration in the study area.

Figure 5. Percentage contribution of Meteorological parameters to radon based on F-values

1.2 Correlation between radon concentration and Meteorological Parameters

The Pearson correlation to quantify the relationships between groundwater radon concentration and meteorological parameters is presented in figure 6. Radon concentration shows a moderate positive correlation with depth ($r \approx 0.65$), reflecting higher radon levels in deeper aquifers due to prolonged water-rock interaction. Atmospheric pressure is strongly negatively correlated with radon ($r \approx -0.63$), indicating that lower pressure enhances radon exhalation from subsurface materials. Wind speed exhibits a moderate negative correlation ($r \approx -0.57$), consistent with increased surface decreasing at higher

wind speeds. Rainfall shows a moderate positive correlation ($r \approx 0.42$), reflecting mobilization of radon into groundwater during moderate recharge, while relative humidity has the strongest negative correlation ($r \approx -0.71$), suggesting that high humidity and recharge dilute radon concentrations. Temperature is weakly negatively correlated with radon ($r \approx -0.12$) and is not statistically significant, reflecting the minimal effect of the narrow temperature range in the tropical climate. These correlations complement the ANOVA and graphical analyses, confirming that depth, relative humidity, wind speed, atmospheric pressure, and rainfall are the primary controls on groundwater radon, while temperature has a minor influence.

Figure 6. Correlation between radon concentration and Meteorological parameters

3.3 Standardized and Unstandardized coefficients of Meteorological Parameters

The summary of the multiple regression analysis results for radon concentration (Bq/m³) are presented in Table 2. Both unstandardized (B) and standardized (Beta) coefficients are reported. The unstandardized coefficients represent the change in radon concentration per unit change in the respective meteorological variable, holding other variables

constant. Depth exhibited the strongest positive influence on radon levels (B = 486.196; Beta = 0.355; p = 0.016), while relative humidity had a negative effect (B = -601.176; Beta = -0.194; p = 0.167). Other predictors, including temperature, pressure, wind speed, and precipitation, showed weak and statistically non-significant associations. These results suggest that depth is the primary meteorological determinant of radon variation in the study area.

Table 2: Regression coefficients for meteorological predictors of radon concentration

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
Constant	-2058070.91	2338896.85	-	-0.880	0.381
Depth	489.196	197.951	0.355	2.456	0.016
Temperature	-891.815	2538.099	-0.036	-0.351	0.726
Pressure	21255.399	23253.38	0.103	0.914	0.303
Wind speed	2687.127	2599.19	0.100	1.034	0.304
Rainfall	994.759	871.045	0.103	1.142	0.256
Relative humidity	-601.176	431.726	-0.194	-1.392	0.167

CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of meteorological parameters on groundwater radon concentration in Oyo State, South-Western Nigeria, using descriptive statistics, graphical analysis, ANOVA, correlation, and regression methods. Radon concentrations ranged from 485.72 to 6205.22 Bq/m³, with the highest levels in moderate–deep aquifer layers and lower values in shallow layers. ANOVA confirmed that these variations were statistically significant, indicating

non-uniform radon distribution influenced by both hydrogeological and environmental factors. Groundwater depth was the primary determinant of radon concentration, with levels increasing in deeper aquifers due to prolonged water–rock interaction and contact with uranium-bearing minerals. Correlation and regression analyses confirmed this, with depth showing a moderate positive correlation (R = 0.65) and a statistically significant regression coefficient (B = 486.196; Beta = 0.355; p = 0.016). Relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, and

rainfall acted as secondary controls. Relative humidity showed the strongest negative correlation ($R = -0.71$), while atmospheric pressure ($R = -0.63$) and wind speed ($R = -0.57$) inversely influenced radon through degassing and surface exchange processes. Rainfall had a moderate positive correlation ($R = 0.42$), reflecting mobilization of radon during recharge events. Temperature exhibited a weak and non-significant effect ($R = -0.12$), indicating minimal influence within the tropical climate range. Generally, groundwater radon in Oyo State is largely controlled by aquifer depth, with meteorological parameters modifying concentrations through dilution, recharge, and degassing. The results highlight the importance of integrating hydrogeological and meteorological factors in radon risk assessment and suggest the need for continuous monitoring to mitigate potential radiological health risks.

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HOW TO CITE: Amodu Fuhke Roseline, Oni Olatunde Michael, Oni Emmanuel Abiodun, Aremu Abraham Adewale*, The Influence of Meteorological Parameters on Groundwater Radon Concentration in Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (4), 48-56. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19388862>